

Albania

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Albania, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Eurydice Report on the national higher education system but complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in national systems, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<http://www.eter-project.eu>) for the period 2017-2019.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

According to Eurydice¹, the Albanian higher education system comprises four types of HEIs:

- University (Universiteti) is a higher education institution that operates in the area of education, scientific research, creative and professional activities. It is composed of at least three main units and of other sub units. Universities conduct basic and applied scientific research activities in compliance with their study programmes, with the higher education law and with their statutes. A university offers study programmes in all higher education study cycles and programmes with a professional character for all cycles.
- Academia (Akademia) is a higher education institution that operates in profiled higher education, scientific research, creative and professional activities. It consists of at least one faculty. Based on its study area, an Academia can offer study programmes for all cycles and study programmes with a professional character.
- University College (Kolegji universitar) consists of main units, basic units and other units as provided in its statutes. It includes at least two faculties. It conducts basic scientific research activities in line with the areas of its study programmes and its statute. Such institutions offer study programmes in the first and/or second study cycle and programmes with a professional character.
- Higher Vocational College (Kolegj Profesional i Lartë) is a higher education institution of vocational nature. It consists of at least two departments. It offers teaching activities that last for 1-2 academic years and correspond respectively with 60 or 120 ECTS. It may be established in affiliation with universities and university colleges. In these cases, it is considered as a main unit of these institutions.

¹https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/eurydice/content/types-higher-education-institutions_en

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

Universities (*universiteti*) are to one half public and the other half private, 70% of them have the right to award PhDs. In total, about 56% of all Albanian HEIs are Universities and equivalent institutions. University Colleges (*kolegj universitar*) account for 27% of all Albanian HEIs, however, none of them awards PhDs. Academies (*academia*), Higher Vocational Colleges (*kolegj profesional i lartë*) and one Higher Education Institution (*shkolla e lartë*) account for the remaining 17% of all HEIs. Besides the universities only two of the Academies award PhDs. Almost two third of all HEIs, mostly Universities, in Albania are private.

Table 1 below provides a quantitative overview of the main institutional characteristics by HEI type. Universities (*universiteti*) are to one half public and the other half private, 70% of them have the right to award PhDs. In total, about 56% of all Albanian HEIs are Universities and equivalent institutions. University Colleges (*kolegj universitar*) account for 27% of all Albanian HEIs, however, none of them awards PhDs. Academies (*academia*), Higher Vocational Colleges (*kolegj profesional i lartë*) and one Higher Education Institution (*shkolla e lartë*) account for the remaining 17% of all HEIs. Besides the universities only two of the Academies award PhDs. Almost two third of all HEIs, mostly Universities, in Albania are private.

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 2019

Category		N	Public	Private	PhD awarding
Academy	akademia	4	3	1	2
Higher Education Institution	shkolla e lartë	1	0	1	0
Higher Vocational College	kolegj profesional i lartë	2	0	2	0
University	universiteti	23	12	11	16
University College	kolegj universitar	11	0	2	0
Total		41	15	26	18

Note: Nehemiah Gateway University is accredited as "Higher Education Institution" by the Quality Assurance Agency in Higher Education (see <https://www.ascal.al/en/hei-list/hei>)

Institutional history. Older and younger institutional types

Data on the HEI foundation year provide information on the history of Albania's higher education and its evolution over time.

Figure 1 below shows that the expansion of the system in terms of the number of HEIs is relatively recent and displays three distinct patterns of expansion. First, the oldest Albanian university, the Agricultural University of Tirana, dates back to 1951, starting a first period of university foundations until 1971 (8 Universities). The second wave of expansion started in 1991 with the foundation of 14 Universities. Third, nearly all other HEIs (except the Academy of Armed Forces, established in 1958) were founded after 2005.

Figure 1. Foundation year of HEIs by type

How are students distributed?

In contrast to the number of institutions, in terms of the number of students enrolled, Universities still account for 94% of all students and University Colleges (*kolegj universitar*) for 3%. The other institutional types play a relatively minor role in the aggregate (see Figure 2). While almost two thirds of the Albanian HEIs in ETER are private, these enrol only 20% of the students and, therefore, play a limited role in the national higher education system.

According to different institutional mandates, we no systematic differences between educational levels can be observed: In total, Universities account for 95% of the bachelor students and 94% of the master students, while doctorates are within the remit of Universities. According to the legal status of the HEIs, the share of bachelor students in private HEIS (27%) outnumbers, then the share of master students (16%).

Figure 2. Students by level and type of HEI, 2019

Changing roles over time

When observed through the lens of the number of students, data show a pattern of decrease with the number of enrolled students. While increasing by 13% from 2011 to 2014, an overall decrease by 10% is

observable between 2011 and 2019, with a slight increase of the share of University Colleges (*kolegi universitar*) from 1% to 3% of the students enrolled.

Figure 3. Share of students enrolled by institutional type

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